

1 On the enticing power of spatial Rao's Q to
2 compute multivariate ecosystem heterogeneity:
3 maths and stats

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15 May 21, 2024

16 **Abstract**

17 Spatio-ecological heterogeneity has a significant impact on vari-
18 ous ecosystem properties, such as biodiversity patterns, variability in
19 ecosystem resources, and species distributions. Given this perspec-
20 tive, remote sensing has gained widespread recognition as a powerful
21 tool for assessing the spatial heterogeneity of ecosystems by analyzing
22 pixel variability in both space and, potentially, time. Several mea-
23 sures of spatial heterogeneity have been proposed, broadly categorized
24 into abundance-related measures (e.g., Shannon's H) and dispersion-
25 related measures (e.g., Variance). A measure that integrates both
26 abundance and distance information is the Rao's quadratic entropy
27 (Rao's Q index). The question arises as to why one should use a com-
28 plex measure that considers multiple dimensions and couples abun-
29 dance and distance measurements instead of relying solely on simple
30 dispersion-based measures of heterogeneity. This paper sheds light
31 on the spatial Rao's Q index from various perspectives, with a par-
32 ticular emphasis on its statistical properties. The main objective is
33 to theoretically demonstrate the strength of Rao's Q index in mea-
34 suring heterogeneity, taking into account all its potential facets and
35 applications, including: (i) integrating multivariate data, (ii) apply-
36 ing differential weighting to pixels, and (iii) considering differential
37 weighting of spectral distances.

38 **Keywords:** biodiversity; diversity metrics; ecosystem heterogeneity; re-
39 mote sensing; spatial statistics.

40 **1 Introduction: measuring spatio-ecological** 41 **heterogeneity**

42 Spatio-ecological heterogeneity plays a significant role in shaping various
43 ecosystem properties, including the distribution of species (Kumar et al.,
44 2006), the habitat structure (Deák et al. , 2021) and the variability of ecosys-
45 tem elements (Turner et al., 2013). From this point of view, remote sensing
46 has been widely acknowledged as a powerful tool to measure the spatial het-
47 erogeneity of ecosystems based on pixel variability in space and, potentially,
48 in time (Skidmore et al., 2021).

49 Numerous methods for assessing spatial heterogeneity have been sug-
50 gested, and they can be broadly categorized into two groups: those linked
51 to abundance (e.g., Shannon’s H, Shannon et al., 1948) and those linked to
52 dispersion (e.g., Variance). A measure coupling such information is Rao’s
53 quadratic entropy (hereafter also referred to as Rao’s Q index, (Rao, 1982)),
54 in which both the abundance and the pairwise distance of objects is con-
55 sidered (see Equation 1). The potential of such a measure has been widely
56 acknowledged by ecologists to measure biodiversity, in particular when con-
57 sidering functional diversity measures based on traits (Botta-Dukát, 2005).
58 Concerning spatio-ecological heterogeneity measurement, Rocchini et al. (2017)
59 first proposed to extend the Rao’s Q index to a spatial (2D) dimension. In

60 practical terms, given any kind of remote sensing data treated as a matrix, a
61 moving window (kernel) can be passed over such a matrix and the Rao's Q
62 index can be calculated in a neighbourhood. The founding principle in the
63 translation from plant communities to spatio-ecological diversity is that pix-
64 els are thought as individual units - as biological individuals in Rao (1982) -
65 and their reflectance value is treated as species/class in Rocchini et al., 2022.

66 Spatial Rao's Q has then been widely used to relate spatial heterogeneity
67 to ecosystem properties like local (Conti et al., 2021) and global (Randin
68 et al., 2020) biodiversity patterns, plant structural properties (Torresani et
69 al., 2023), plant species compositional turnover (Wang et al., 2022), plant
70 functional diversity (Hauser et al., 2021), temporal variations of dissimilar-
71 ities of plant communities (Rossi et al., 2021), coastal vegetation dynamics
72 (Malavasi et al., 2021), tropical (Pangtey et al., 2023) and alpine (Torresani
73 et al. , 2018) trees diversity and marine habitat changes (Doxa et al., 2002).
74 The question that emerges is why researchers should opt for the adoption of a
75 complex measure that encompasses multiple dimensions and integrates both
76 abundance and distance measurements, rather than relying on straightfor-
77 ward dispersion-based measures of heterogeneity, such as variance (Graham
78 et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2022).

79 In this paper we want to shed light on the spatial Rao's Q index from
80 different perspectives, with a focus on its statistical properties. In particular,

81 our aim is to theoretically demonstrate the power of the Rao's Q index in
82 measuring heterogeneity accounting for all of its potential facets and appli-
83 cations, such as: (i) multivariate data integration, (ii) differential weighting
84 of pixels, and (iii) differential weighting of spectral distances. The flow of
85 the presented formula is available in Figure 1.

86 **2 What does the Rao's Q index actually mea-** 87 **sure?**

88 In the realm of remote sensing applications, the process of discerning the
89 spatial distribution of diversity within a digital image, specifically identi-
90 fying areas of the image that exhibit higher diversity compared to others,
91 commonly involves the computation of diversity indices. These indices are
92 typically calculated within specific regions of interest or by utilizing moving
93 windows (Figure 2, (Rocchini et al., 2021)). Accordingly, given a moving win-
94 dow of any size and shape composed by N pixels, the Rao's Q index Q can
95 be defined as the expected spectral dissimilarity between two pixels drawn
96 at random with replacement from the window:

$$Q = \sum_{i,j}^N \frac{1}{N} \times \frac{1}{N} \times d_{ij} \quad (1)$$

97 where $\frac{1}{N}$ is the probability of drawing pixel i (or j) out of N pixels and d_{ij}
98 is the spectral dissimilarity between pixels i and j such that $d_{ij} = d_{ji}$ (i.e.
99 d_{ij} is symmetric) and $d_{ii} = 0$ (the spectral dissimilarity of a pixel with itself
100 equals zero).

101 Therefore, according to Equation 1, in its simplest formulation, Rao's Q
102 index is nothing more than the mean spectral dissimilarity among the N pix-
103 els in the moving window, including the dissimilarity of one pixel with itself.
104 The dissimilarity d_{ij} can be computed either from a single spectral band as
105 the difference in values between two pixels or in a multivariate spectral space
106 by means of one of the many multivariate dissimilarity coefficients used in
107 exploratory data analysis (see e.g., Legendre & Legendre, 2012). Hence, un-
108 like more standard diversity indices which are calculated on a single band at
109 a time, the Rao's Q index can accommodate multivariate differences between
110 digital numbers (DNs).

111 It is easily shown that for a fixed number of pixels N , the relationship
112 between the Rao's Q index and the expected spectral dissimilarity between
113 two pixels drawn at random without replacement from the window $Q' =$
114 $\sum_{i \neq j}^N \frac{1}{N} \times \frac{1}{N-1} \times d_{ij}$ (i.e. the standard mean dissimilarity among the N
115 pixels) is equal to:

$$Q' = \frac{N}{N-1} \times Q \quad (2)$$

116 In the univariate case, if the dissimilarity in the reflectance values (DNs)
 117 of a single spectral band is computed as half the squared Euclidean distance
 118 $d_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \times (DN_i - DN_j)^2$, the Rao's Q index is identical to variance, which
 119 is routinely used in remote sensing applications to compute the spatial com-
 120 plexity of digital images (Rocchini et al., 2017):

$$Q = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} \frac{1}{N} \times \frac{1}{N} \times (DN_i - DN_j)^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i (DN_i - \overline{DN})^2 \quad (3)$$

121 where \overline{DN} is the mean spectral reflectance of the N pixels: $\overline{DN} =$
 122 $\frac{1}{N} \sum_i DN_i$. Accordingly, the Rao's Q index can be interpreted as a distance-
 123 based multivariate generalization of the variance of a quantitative variable,
 124 such as the DNs of one or more spectral bands. As such, it represents the
 125 dispersion of DNs in multivariate space, which can be calculated with a
 126 wide variety of dissimilarity measures of choice. Champely & Chessel (2002)
 127 further showed that, under particular circumstances, quadratic diversity cor-
 128 responds to the mean distance of the N pixels from the centroid of the DNs
 129 distribution in multivariate space.

130 **3 Potential applications**

131 **3.1 Multivariate data integration**

132 The properties of the Rao's Q index have been explored by many authors
133 (Shimatani, 2001; Champely & Chessel, 2002; Pavoine et al., 2005; Ricotta
134 & Szeidl, 2006, 2009; Pavoine & Bonsall, 2009; Rao, 2010; Pavoine, 2012;
135 Pavoine & Ricotta, 2014), and the reader is referred to these papers for
136 additional details. Nonetheless, in a remote sensing context, there are some
137 aspects in which the high flexibility of quadratic diversity may be helpful for
138 exploring remotely sensed landscape complexity.

139 Compared to more classical univariate measures, the main advantage of
140 the Rao's Q index is that with quadratic entropy one can calculate land-
141 scape complexity using multiple spectral bands of a remotely sensed image
142 simultaneously. By using appropriate dissimilarity measures, this multivari-
143 ate approach can be further extended to integrate a mixture of different data
144 sources in the index calculation, such as raw multispectral bands, categorical
145 land use types derived from image classification or land use maps, ordinal
146 values of landscape conservation status, surface temperatures obtained from
147 thermal sensors, or LiDAR data on the vegetation structural complexity
148 (Torresani et al., 2020) . In addition, among the several dissimilarity coef-
149 ficients that have been developed to handle mixed data sets (Gower, 1971;

150 Carranza et al., 1998; Podani, 1999) some of them (see e.g., Pavoine et al.,
 151 2009) allow the inclusion of variable weights for the various data sources such
 152 that the different variables may contribute differently to the calculation of
 153 multivariate landscape complexity (see Rocchini et al., 2017 for an example).
 154 In this way, if some variables are more important than others in determin-
 155 ing landscape complexity and functioning, then they should be given greater
 156 relevance for the calculation of quadratic diversity (Pavoine et al., 2009).

157 **3.2 Differential weighting of pixels**

158 In Eq. 1, the weights w_i associated to each pixel are all equal to $w_i =$
 159 $\frac{1}{N}$, which is the probability of drawing pixel i out of the N pixels in the
 160 moving window. Nonetheless, Rao's quadratic entropy (intended as the mean
 161 dissimilarity among the N pixels) can also be calculated by weighting pixels
 162 differently in a way that depends on the specific user requirements. In this
 163 case, Eq. 1 becomes:

$$Q = \sum_{i,j}^N w_i \times w_j \times d_{ij} \quad (4)$$

164 with $0 \leq w_i \leq 1$ and $\sum_i^N w = 1$.

165 The weights associated with the different pixels may reflect properties as
 166 diverse as their conservation status, land use, vegetation cover, etc. Hence,

167 according to Eq. 4, the N pixels are not all of the same importance, but some
168 pixels are more important than others in determining landscape diversity.

169 In this framework, the contribution of pixel i to the overall spectral di-
170 versity of a given region/window (i.e. its spectral originality O_i) can be
171 summarized as the mean dissimilarity between pixel i and a second pixel
172 drawn at random with replacement from the window:

$$O_i = \sum_j^N w_j \times d_{ij} \quad (5)$$

173 Accordingly, the Rao's Q index in Eq. 4 can also be interpreted as the
174 mean spectral originality of the N pixels in the moving window (see Ricotta
175 et al., 2016), such that:

$$Q = \sum_i^N w_i \times O_i = \sum_{i,j}^N w_i \times w_j \times d_{ij} \quad (6)$$

176 **3.3 Differential weighting of spectral distances: a para-** 177 **metric version of the Rao's Q index**

178 As shown in Eq. 1, the Rao's Q index basically summarizes the mean spectral
179 dissimilarity among the N pixels in a given region/window. However, in
180 some cases, it might be useful to confer to higher distances a higher weight
181 enhancing the highest possible gradient of diversity.

182 One method for attributing a different relevance to the higher spectral
 183 dissimilarities d_{ij} compared to lower dissimilarities has been first proposed by
 184 Rocchini et al. (2021). Their proposal starts from the observation of Guiasu
 185 & Guiasu (2011) that Rao's Q index can be described as a linear function of
 186 the combined probabilities of all pairs of pixels (see Rocchini et al., 2021):

$$Q = \sum_{i,j}^N \frac{1}{N} \times \frac{1}{N} \times d_{ij} = \sum_{i,j}^N \pi_{ij} \times d_{ij} \quad (7)$$

187 where π_{ij} is the combined probability of selecting pixels i and j in this or-
 188 der (Guiasu & Guiasu, 2011). Consequently, based on Equation 7, quadratic
 189 diversity is derived as the arithmetic mean of spectral dissimilarities d_{ij} com-
 190 puted between all pixel pairs i and j .

191 In order to assign a different level of relevance to higher dissimilarities
 192 compared to lower dissimilarities, a natural way consists of substituting the
 193 arithmetic mean in Eq. 7 with a power mean or generalized mean (Hardy et
 194 al., 1952):

$$Q_\alpha = \left(\sum_{i,j}^N \pi_{ij} \times d_{ij}^\alpha \right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \quad (8)$$

195 with $\alpha > 0$.

196 Each generalized mean Q_α always lies between the smallest and largest
 197 of the original values: $\min d_{ij} \leq Q_\alpha \leq \max d_{ij}$ and, for increasingly high

198 values of the parameter α , progressively assigns higher relevance to higher
199 dissimilarities in the calculation of quadratic diversity.

200 In this view, some characteristic values of the parameter α recover some
201 more standard concepts of means. For instance, for α approaching 0, quadratic
202 diversity approaches the geometric mean $Q_0 = \sqrt[N]{\prod_{ij} \pi_{ij} \times d_{ij}^2}$; for $\alpha = 1$ we
203 get the standard arithmetic mean in Eq. 7; for $\alpha = 2$, we get the cubic mean
204 $Q_2 = \sqrt{\sum_{i,j} \pi_{ij} \times d_{ij}^2}$, while for $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$, we get $Q_\infty \rightarrow \max d_{ij}$.

205 Hence, the generalized version of quadratic diversity embodies a contin-
206 uum of potential diversity measures that differ in their sensitivity to higher
207 and lower spectral dissimilarities such that by varying the parameter α we
208 can potentially optimize the relationship between remotely sensed landscape
209 diversity and ecosystem properties.

210 4 Outlook

211 When using Rao's quadratic entropy, three main important possibilities can
212 be applied: (i) the possibility to use it in a multivariate space and generalize
213 it, (ii) the possibility to differentially weight pixel values, (iii) the possibility
214 to differentially weight distances in the spectral space.

215 Concerning the first point, the Rao's Q index is a multivariate notion that
216 puts a number of traditional measures of remotely sensed landscape hetero-

217 geneity under the same umbrella. As such, it is not an alternative to more
218 classical measures of remotely sensed landscape complexity, such as variance
219 or the mean spectral dissimilarity among pixels. In fact, a univariate version
220 of the Rao's Q index, calculated on a single digital layer, should reduce to any
221 metric based on data dispersion. On the contrary, the implicit properties of
222 Rao's Q index as a multivariate and potentially generalized measure of het-
223 erogeneity would enhance the capabilities of measuring landscape diversity
224 from drone or satellite imagery (see subsection 3.1), adding information to
225 the simple contrast derived from univariate measures.

226 Furthermore, with respect to other measures, the Rao's Q index allows
227 to differentially weight pixels. When using meaningful landscape variables
228 (e.g., some land use class of interest) or known properties of spectral response
229 in a certain band, a differential weight of pixels suspected to be related to
230 peculiar ecological processes can enhance their strength, relying on e.g. a
231 spatial weighting matrix (Bauman et al., 2018).

232 From this point of view, a different weight to larger distances has also a
233 well grounded ecological meaning. In fact, larger distances account for the
234 highest possible turnover in a species or spectral community, and are there-
235 fore of valuable importance to describe the gradient of diversity (Rocchini,
236 2007). Moreover, just adding a single category to the set of categories in
237 the window of analysis can lead to a wide increase of diversity in case its

238 distance from the others is higher than the (previous) mean distance (Shi-
239 matani, 1999; Pavoine et al., 2009). Hence, focusing on maximum distances
240 can help evaluating potential trends of β -diversity (spatial turnover) other-
241 wise lost when only considering mean distances (Baselga et al., 2013). More-
242 over, using different weights on distances can help discover all the potential
243 facets of (Rao's Q index) spectral diversity on the entire cloud of pixels. In
244 other words, weighting distances can help conveying information on the lower
245 and upper boundaries of diversity. This is not only true for diversity patterns
246 measured at the ecosystem or species levels, but more generally for any model
247 relating species to habitats. In these cases, different distance weighting leads
248 to different patterns in the relationship between habitat cover and species
249 abundance which is generally multi-scalar (Aue et al., 2012).

250 The relationship of species with habitats which rule their life can be
251 explicitly estimated through remote sensing (Skidmore et al., 2021); applying
252 proper measures like the Rao's Q index could enhance the power of remotely
253 sensed data for species diversity estimate at different spatial scales and in a
254 multivariate ecological space. This could be powered by linking species in the
255 field with their spectral signatures, based on a concept known as "spectral
256 species", which represent the particular spectral signal of every plant species
257 on the ground (Féret & Asner, 2014; Rocchini et al., 2022). Starting from this
258 concept, maps of alpha- or beta-diversity could be derived by the Rao's Q

259 index applied to hyperspectral data based on a high amount of different bands
260 ensuring to capture peaks related to each spectral (and ground) species.

261 Remote sensing data are particularly powerful in measuring diversity
262 changes in space and time as they provides for long term images at con-
263 stant intervals. That is why a plethora of studies has used them as ancillary
264 variable for biodiversity in the field (see Gillespie et al., 2008 for a review).
265 However, applying simplistic measures would definitively hide a wide part of
266 the potential facets of diversity. From this point of view, the use of Rao's Q
267 entropy catches a wider spectrum of the diversity pattern. Moreover, from
268 a practical point of view, this measure is now available in different open
269 source packages concerning both species (e.g., the R packages `FD`, `picante`,
270 `SYNCASA`, `Rarefy`) and spectral (e.g., the R packages `rasterdiv`) variability
271 (Box 1).

272 Criticism arises about the real match between species and spectral di-
273 versity. In fact, in some cases, spectral heterogeneity does not necessarily
274 correspond to species diversity in the field. In other words, heterogeneity
275 patterns derived from the spectral signal could be related to land use classes
276 or objects which do not reflect diversity patterns, e.g. wide urban areas
277 (Rocchini et al., 2021) or seminatural areas with plantations mixed to nat-
278 ural forests (Fassnacht et al., 2022). Of course, in this view, remote sensing
279 cannot be generally seen as a surrogate for species diversity measurement in

280 the field but rather as preliminary exploratory for a first information about
281 the spectral signatures of plant species.

282 **5 Conclusion**

283 Any index of diversity should account for differences among categories as well
284 as the proportions of such categories (Pavoine, 2012). From this point of view,
285 the main lesson learned is that Rao's Q index satisfies these requirements
286 from several points of view, guaranteeing not only to make use of relative
287 abundances and distances, but also to tune the index with a differential
288 weighting of both categories (pixel values) and (spectral) distances.

289 Moreover, testing the interaction of different factors accounting for diver-
290 sity is an important component of any measurement of diversity (Legendre
291 & Anderson, 1999). Using the Rao's Q index allows for interpretation of
292 results on diversity based on a set of different spatial layers interacting to
293 shape biological diversity in the field.

294 Finally, a generalized version of Rao's Q index allows for the identification
295 of interesting "regions" across the entire diversity spectrum in a multivariate
296 space, revealing hidden insights that may be lost when using point descriptors
297 that overlook the diversity gradient (Rényi, 1961, 1970; Nakamura et al.,
298 2020). While this is a long lasting theme in functional diversity measurement

299 of species communities, we present the first theoretical dissertation of the
300 mathematical properties of the spatial version of Rao's Q index.

301 **Data archiving statement**

302 This is a theoretical paper, hence it does not contain data to be deposited.

303 **Conflict of interest statement**

304 Authors declare no conflict of interest concerning relationship, financial or
305 any other aspect.

306 **Author contributions**

307 Duccio Rocchini and Carlo Ricotta conceptualized and equally contributed
308 to the writing of the manuscript. Michele Torresani provided writing, review,
309 and editing support.

310 **Funding**

311 None

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472 **Box 1 - Available R packages to calculate Rao's**

473 **Q index**

474 **Species level**

- 475 • **adiv**: analysis of community diversity - [https://CRAN.R-project.](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=adiv)
476 [org/package=adiv](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=adiv)
- 477 • **FD**: functional diversity (FD) from multiple traits - [https://CRAN.](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=FD)
478 [R-project.org/package=FD](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=FD)
- 479 • **picante**: community analyses, null-models, traits and evolution - [https:](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=picante)
480 [//CRAN.R-project.org/package=picante](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=picante)
- 481 • **Rarefy**: spatially and non-spatially explicit rarefaction curves using
482 different indices of taxonomic, functional and phylogenetic diversity -
483 <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=Rarefy>
- 484 • **SYNCASA**: metacommunities analysis using functional traits and phy-
485 logeny of the community components. - [https://CRAN.R-project.](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=SYNCASA)
486 [org/package=SYNCASA](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=SYNCASA)

487 **Spectral level**

- 488 • rasterdiv: diversity indices for numerical matrices - [https://CRAN.](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=rasterdiv)
489 [R-project.org/package=rasterdiv](https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=rasterdiv)

Figure 1: Flowchart of the main formulas described in this paper describing the Rao's Q index formula (Eq. 1) and its main properties (Eq. 2 and 3). Starting from the Rao's Q index, pixels can be differentially weighted (Eq. 4) to give more importance to specific landscape characteristics, with the possibility of calculating the contribution of each pixel (Eq. 5) as well as the spectral originality (sensu Ricotta et al., 2016) of N pixels (Eq. 6). Furthermore, one can assign a differential weight to distances, e.g., to larger distances which account for the highest possible turnover (Eq. 7 and 8).

Figure 2: Description of the moving window approach to calculate any spatial measure in a neighborhood. The first moving window (red) of 3x3 pixels is passed over the original matrix/image and used to calculate a measure, in this case the Rao's Q index, which is attached to the central pixel in output matrix/image. Then, it moves by one step (green and then blue, etc.) and the same approach is applied. The whole process is repeated throughout the entire original matrix/image and leads to a new output with the calculated Rao's Q index. Any odd number of pixels can be used as moving window dimension.